

THE PERCEIVED INFLUENCE OF INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHOD AND THE TECHNOLOGICAL INTEGRATION ON STUDENT ENGAGEMENT OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL IN ENGLISH SUBJECT

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 1

Pages: 63-75

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2541

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13986493

Manuscript Accepted: 09-10-2024

The Perceived Influence of Interactive Teaching Method and The Technological Integration on Student Engagement of Junior High School in English Subject

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Abstract

This study examines the level of interactive teaching method and technological integration and their influence on student engagement in English education among junior high school students at St. Peter's College of Toril Inc. for the school year 2023-2024. It seeks to determine the correlation between teachers' interactive teaching method and student engagement, as well as the correlation between technological integration and student engagement. Finally, the study aims to identify which variable, interactive teaching method or technological integration, significantly influences student engagement. The study employed a quantitative research design, specifically a descriptive correlational design, and analysis methods such as mean score, standard deviation, Pearson's correlation, and regression analysis to determine if there is a significant correlation between teachers' interactive teaching methods and students' engagement levels, as well as investigate the influence of technological integration on student engagement. Findings revealed that interactive teaching methods and technology integration significantly enhance student engagement. Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that educators and schools focus on enhancing student participation and empowerment. High performance in promoting active participation was noted, while improvement is needed in encouraging group project participation. Schools should implement dynamic, collaborative activities and personalized learning experiences. Using the Technology Integration Matrix (TIM) can help future researchers evaluate and optimize technology use in teaching. School administrators should provide engaging technological tools and ongoing teacher training. Emphasizing timely task completion and fostering classroom connections can further enhance engagement. Correlation analysis shows a positive relationship between interactive teaching methods, technological integration, and student engagement, highlighting the importance. Schools should prioritize interactive teaching strategies and integrate technology, supported by professional development, to create engaging learning environments that boost student success.

Keywords: *correlational study, interactive teaching methods, technological integration, student engagement*

Introduction

Secondary education is fundamental in nurturing students' intellectual abilities, social skills, and personal growth (GGI Insights, 2024). In English education for junior high school students, effective classrooms foster excitement and engagement, where educators not only master their subjects but also understand how their teaching strategies influence students' development as independent lifelong learners (Franklin & Harrington, 2019). A critical component of this educational process is student engagement, which drives learning outcomes and overall student achievement.

Student engagement, characterized by the energy and effort students invest in learning, is shaped by various behavioral, cognitive, and affective factors (Bond et al., 2020). Interpersonal relationships, learning activities, and the environment influence these factors. Engaged students are more likely to participate actively, experience emotional well-being, and achieve intellectual growth, underscoring the importance of understanding and fostering engagement in educational settings.

Interactive teaching methods, which involve students actively in the learning process through participation, collaboration, and critical thinking, have gained global recognition for their effectiveness in improving learning outcomes (Kamran et al., 2022). These methods are inclusive, catering to diverse learning styles, and have been widely adopted in various secondary schools. By promoting active engagement, interactive teaching methods ensure deeper information retention and create a dynamic learning environment.

As conceptualized by TPACK, technology integration refers to the strategic use of technological tools to enhance teaching and learning (Zhou et al., 2022). This approach combines technology with pedagogy to achieve specific educational goals, improve teaching methods, and increase students' digital literacy. In the context of English education, thoughtful technology integration can make learning more engaging, reflective, and relevant to students who are increasingly familiar with digital tools.

The literature highlights the significance of interactive teaching methods and technology integration in fostering student engagement. For instance, Kamran et al. (2023) emphasize that interactive methods enhance student engagement by encouraging collaborative learning and critical thinking. Similarly, Katyara et al. (2023) note that digital tools like videos, blogs, and online tutorials can support reflective participation and metacognitive strategies, enriching the learning experience.

Educators have also explored the impact of these approaches in the Philippine context. Obenza et al. (2019) found that data-driven strategies based on student engagement can create personalized learning environments, leading to improved student outcomes.

However, challenges such as limited resources, infrastructure, and varying levels of teacher training and technology expertise still need to be addressed to integrate technology effectively (Dublar, 2023).

This study aims to fill the research gap by examining the combined influence of interactive teaching methods and technology integration on student engagement in English education among junior high school students. This research provides valuable insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers by identifying the most impactful factors, ultimately enhancing educational practices and student engagement.

Research Questions

This study examines the perceived influence of teachers' interactive teaching method and technological integration on students' engagement in English education among junior high school students at St. Peter's College of Toril Inc. for the school year 2023-2024. It seeks to determine the correlation between teachers' interactive teaching method and students' engagement levels and investigate the influence of technological integration on student engagement.

Additionally, the study aims to identify which variable, interactive teaching method or technological integration, strongly influences student engagement. Specifically, this study answers the following research question:

1. What is the level of teacher's interactive teaching method for Junior High School English Students? Specifically in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. promotion of active participation;
 - 1.2. creating a positive classroom environment; and
 - 1.3. fostering student empowerment?
2. What is the level of teacher's technological Integration in Junior High School English Students? Specifically in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. use of technology in teaching learning;
 - 2.2. technology enhanced assessment; and
 - 2.3. fostering student empowerment?
3. What is the level of student engagement among junior high school English students?
 - 3.1. behavioral engagement;
 - 3.2. cognitive engagement; and
 - 3.3. emotional engagement?
4. Is there a significant influence of the teachers' interactive teaching method on student engagement in Junior High School in English?
5. Is there a significant influence of the teachers' technological integration on student engagement in Junior High School in English?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative research design, specifically a descriptive correlational design, to meet its objectives by generating numerical data and concrete facts through scientific methods (Ahmed, 2019). This approach aimed to determine causal connections between variables using mathematical, computational, and statistical methodologies. The correlational method, a non-experimental observational study, was used to predict and explain the influence between independent variables (interactive teaching methods and technological integration) and the dependent variable (student engagement) (Seeram, 2019). Additionally, linear regression analysis, a quantitative method for determining correlations between variables, was utilized to establish the relationships among the variables (Mu et al., 2019). This research design is appropriate for the study as it offers precise measurements and helps establish causal relationships, with survey questionnaires collecting numerical data to quantify the relationships between the variables.

Respondents

This study employed the stratified sampling method to identify respondents, ensuring fair representation across different grade levels and sections by dividing the population into homogenous subgroups, or "strata," and randomly selecting a representative sample from each (Simkus, 2023). This technique allows for deeper analysis and a broader understanding of each group within the population. The researchers used Slovin's formula with a 0.05 margin of error to determine a sample size of 223 from a total population of 504 Junior High School students for the 2023-2024 school year. Proportional allocation was used to determine the number of participants in each stratum, ensuring each subgroup was adequately represented in proportion to its size in the total population.

Instrument

The researchers developed a custom survey instrument for this study, as existing tools from the literature align well with the overall study design. The instrument consists of four parts to facilitate data collection effectively. The first part introduces the study to respondents, including essential details such as the title, primary goals, objectives, and information about the researchers. The second

part assesses the level of interactive teaching methods used by teachers for Junior High School English students in Grades 7, 8, 9, and 10, with 15 statements grouped according to the study's indicators: promotion of active participation, creating a positive classroom environment, and fostering student empowerment.

The survey employs a 5-point Likert scale to gauge attitudes and opinions, providing five response options from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree," which allows for a nuanced understanding of respondents' feelings and viewpoints. The Likert scale is detailed in Table 1, with numerical values assigned to each description: 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Moderately Agree), 3 (Agree), 2 (Disagree), and 1 (Strongly Disagree). This approach effectively captures the degree of agreement or disagreement, supporting the study's objective to understand the impact of interactive teaching methods.

Procedure

The researchers underwent several steps to gather data for this study. First, they sought permission from the Dean of the High School of the Private and Catholic Institution by writing an endorsement letter to conduct the study on "The Perceived Influence of Interactive Teaching Method and Technological Integration on Student Engagement of Junior High School in English Subject." They then requested a list of Junior High School students for the 2023-2024 academic year from the registrar's office to identify potential respondents. Following approval, they administered and retrieved questionnaires from the selected participants, ensuring clarity and assistance to maintain data integrity and minimize biases. After collecting the questionnaires, the researchers tabulated the results, organized and summarized the data using statistical tools or software, and utilized visual aids like graphs or charts for clarity. The final phase involved writing the research paper, synthesizing the study's purpose, methodology, results, and conclusions into a cohesive narrative, and adhering to academic standards to ensure credibility and contribution to existing knowledge.

Data Analysis

The data analysis utilized several statistical tools. Mean Score and Standard Deviation were used to address problems 1, 2, and 3, providing descriptive information about the sample and its variability (Andrade, 2020). For problems 4 and 5 and hypotheses 1 and 2, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient evaluated the linear correlation between variables, measuring the strength and direction of their relationship (Chen & Anderson, 2023). Finally, Linear Regression was used to address problem 6 and hypothesis 3, examining how changes in independent variables affect the dependent variable, thereby quantifying their relationship (Aslam et al., 2018).

Ethical Considerations

According to Bachelor Print (2022), ethical considerations in research refer to guidelines and principles ensuring research adherence to established rules and the well-being of participants. Following guidelines from the SPCT Research and Publications Office based on Ethical Consideration (2024), this study engaged Junior High School students to examine the impact of interactive teaching methods and technological integration on their engagement. Informed consent and assent were obtained from students and parents, emphasizing voluntary participation and the right to withdraw without consequences. Risks were minimized by conducting surveys during non-instructional times and ensuring confidentiality per RA 10173, the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Data was handled securely and destroyed post-study. The stratified sampling technique was used for selecting respondents, and transparency was maintained throughout, with conflict-of-interest procedures in place.

The researchers, enrolled in St. Peter's College of Toril, received guidance from course mentors, advisers, and a statistician to ensure the study's reliability. Adequate facilities and resources were utilized, and community involvement was respected by considering local customs. Data gathering involved seeking permission, administering and retrieving questionnaires, tabulating results, and writing the paper, adhering to academic standards.

Results and Discussion

Level of Interactive Teaching Method

The following table shows the result of every statement/question provided per indicator regarding the level of Interactive Teaching Methods of Junior High School English Students. The results are the following:

Table 1. *Level of Interactive Teaching Method: Promoting Active Participation*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
My teachers encourage us to participate actively during class discussions and activities.	4.35	0.713	Very High
My teachers' interactive approach provides a more enjoyable learning experience.	4.13	0.818	High
My teachers encourage us to contribute actively to group activities and collaborative learning tasks.	4.17	0.815	High
My teachers encourage seeking opportunities to participate in discussions and activities during class sessions.	4.13	0.816	High
My teachers' interactive approach has enhanced my willingness to participate in group projects and presentations.	3.96	0.889	High
Overall Indicator Mean	4.15	0.821	High

Table 1 shows that Junior High School English students rated their teachers' interactive teaching methods highly, with the highest mean score of 4.35 for the statement, "My teachers encourage us to participate actively during class discussions and activities." This suggests that students feel their teachers effectively promote active participation, which Gurcan et al. (2023) associate with improved academic outcomes and essential skills like critical thinking and collaboration. In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.96 was given to the statement about teachers enhancing participation in group projects and presentations, indicating room for improvement. Kyleen Gray (2021) suggests that teachers must make interactive approaches more engaging and relevant to boost participation.

The average mean score of 4.15 indicates a high level of interactive teaching methods. Blog (2023) supports this by recommending strategies like think-pair-share and group projects to foster student interaction and engagement. Nickerson (2024) further highlights the importance of the social context in learning, where students actively shape and are shaped by their educational environment.

Table 2. *Level of Interactive Teaching Method: Creating a Positive Classroom*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
My teachers encourage open communication and participation among students.	4.13	0.822	High
My teachers create an environment where everyone feels comfortable expressing his/her ideas and opinions during classes.	3.92	0.874	High
The interactive nature of the class fosters collaboration and teamwork among students.	3.90	0.941	High
Our teachers create a classroom atmosphere that is conducive to active learning through interactive methods.	3.91	0.833	High
My teachers' interactive methods contribute to a positive classroom environment.	4.09	0.852	High
Overall Indicator Mean	3.99	0.870	High

Table 2 shows that Junior High School English students rated their teachers' interactive teaching methods highly in creating a positive classroom environment. The highest mean score of 4.13 was for the statement, "My teachers encourage open communication and participation among students," indicating a strong effectiveness in fostering a supportive environment. İşeri and Tabak (n.d.) emphasize that positive student-teacher relationships enhance the classroom atmosphere. Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.90 was for the statement, "The interactive nature of the class fosters collaboration and teamwork among students." This suggests that while interactive methods are generally effective, there is room for improvement in promoting student collaboration. Smith et al. (2018) highlight that more focus is needed on enhancing teamwork through interactive activities.

Overall, the average mean score of 3.99 reflects a high level of interactive teaching methods in creating a positive classroom environment. Qiu (2022) notes that a supportive and welcoming classroom climate promotes engagement and collaboration. As Widodo, Arif, and Astuti (2024) discussed, Social Cognitive Theory supports this by highlighting the role of social interactions in learning. Maintaining a positive classroom environment is crucial for effective interactive teaching methods.

Table 3. *Level of Interactive Teaching Method: Fostering Student Empowerment*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Active engagement and communication, both with teachers and among classmates, strengthen my confidence in expressing my ideas and opinions.	3.92	0.965	High
I feel valued as a student when my input is incorporated into the learning process through interactive activities.	3.89	0.884	High
Engaging in discussions, hands-on activities, and collaborative projects fosters a sense of accountability for my learning outcomes and cultivates ownership of the learning process.	4.02	0.805	High
I had opportunities to explore topics of interest and personalize my learning experience.	4.05	0.801	High
My teachers provided constructive feedback that helped me take control of my learning journey and academic progress.	3.91	0.945	High
Overall Indicator Mean	3.96	0.883	High

Table 3 indicates a high level of interactive teaching methods in fostering student empowerment among Junior High School English students. The highest mean score of 4.05 was for the statement, "I had opportunities to explore topics of interest and personalize my learning experience," suggesting that students feel empowered to tailor their learning. Patrick, Kennedy, and Powell (2020) support this, noting that personalized learning enhances engagement and student empowerment. Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.89 was "I feel valued as a student when my input is incorporated into the learning process through interactive activities." Freeman et al. (2018) highlight that while integrating student input is essential, making students feel valued is still room for improvement.

Overall, the average mean score of 3.96 reflects a high level of interactive teaching methods promoting student empowerment. Fangfang and Hoben (2020) emphasize that active student involvement allows students to influence their learning, though balancing agency with opportunities for critical thinking is essential. This is supported by "SciSpace (n.d.)," which explains that social cognitive theory emphasizes learning through social interactions and the influence of personal, behavioral, and environmental factors.

Table 4 reveals that the highest mean value of 4.15, with an SD of 0.821, is for promoting active participation. This suggests that interactive teaching methods in Junior High School English classes are highly effective in encouraging student involvement. Blog (2023) supports this by noting that think-pair-share and cooperative learning significantly enhance student interaction and engagement. This approach fosters a dynamic learning environment where students feel motivated to actively participate and contribute.

Table 4. Overall Level of Interactive Teaching Method

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description
Promoting Active Participation	4.15	0.821	High
Creating a Positive Classroom Environment	3.99	0.870	High
Fostering Student Empowerment	3.96	0.883	High
Overall variable mean	4.03	0.279	High

Conversely, the lowest mean value of 3.96, with an SD of 0.883, is for fostering student empowerment, though it still indicates a high level of effectiveness. Fangfang and Hoben (2020) highlight that while student empowerment is essential, it must be balanced with diverse learning experiences to avoid turning education into a rigid process. The overall mean of 4.03, with an SD of 0.826, underscores that interactive teaching methods are highly effective. Chi et al. (2018) and Nickerson (2024) emphasize that these methods improve student engagement by creating positive learning environments and aligning with Social Cognitive Theory, which suggests students learn best through active, interactive experiences.

Level of Technological Integration

The following table shows the result of every question provided per indicator regarding the level of Technological Integration of Junior High School English Students. The results are as follows:

Table 5. Level of Technological Integration: Use of Technology in Teaching Learning

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
My teacher regularly uses various technological tools in our classes.	4.12	0.846	High
My teachers' use of technology in the class encourages me to participate.	3.93	0.838	High
My teachers' use of technology enhances the effectiveness of teaching.	4.20	0.780	Very high
My teachers use technology-based materials, such as video lectures, more effectively than traditional lectures.	4.07	0.885	High
Our teachers' use of technology allows for better communication between teachers and students.	4.11	0.836	High
Overall indicator mean	4.08	0.841	High

Table 5 indicates that the highest mean value of 4.20, with an SD of 0.780, is for the statement, "My teachers' use of technology enhances the teaching effectiveness," suggesting very high levels of technological integration. Pandita and Kiran (2023) support this, showing that digital learning platforms significantly boost student engagement and learning outcomes. In contrast, the lowest mean value of 3.93, with an SD of 0.838, is for the statement, "My teachers' use of technology in the class encourages me to participate," which still indicates a high level of technological integration. Durff and Carter (2019) explain that challenges such as teachers' confidence and experience with technology can impact student participation, highlighting barriers to effective technology use.

Overall, the mean value of 4.08, with an SD of 0.841, indicates a high level of technological integration in teaching. Blasiman et al. (2018) found that students generally respond positively to technology-based materials, enhancing engagement and effectiveness. Schunk and Usher (2019) support these findings with Social Cognitive Theory, emphasizing that the social environment, including technology use, plays a crucial role in motivation and learning.

Table 6. Level of Technological Integration: Technology Enhanced Assessment

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
Our teachers frequently use technology for assessment purposes.	4.15	0.828	High
Our teachers' use of various technological platforms in our quizzes and other assessments contributes to a fair and unbiased environment.	4.10	0.753	High
Our teachers' use of various technological platforms allows for variations in assessments and quizzes.	3.99	0.785	High
Our teachers' use of various technological platforms provides a more engaging assessment experience.	3.99	0.846	High
Our teacher's use of various technological platforms positively impacts assessment quality.	4.05	0.823	High
Overall indicator mean	4.05	0.809	High

Table 6 reveals that the highest mean value of 4.15, with an SD of 0.828, is for the statement, "Our teachers frequently use technology for assessment purposes," indicating high levels of technological integration in assessments. The Social Cognitive Theory Model supports this, suggesting that consistent use of technology for assessments, such as educational apps and online quizzes, helps students develop a sense of mastery. Conversely, the lowest mean value of 3.99, with an SD of 0.785, is for the statement, "Our teachers' use of various technological platforms allows for variations in assessment and quizzes." This still reflects a high level of technological integration but highlights challenges such as technical issues and lack of familiarity that can affect student engagement, as Abuhassna and Yahaya (2020) noted.

The mean value of 4.05, with an SD of 0.809, indicates a high level of technological integration in technology-enhanced assessments. Abuhassna et al. (2020) support this by noting that assessment technology is effective and positively received by students, enhancing

learning and engagement. Technology integration aligns with Social Cognitive Theory, which emphasizes the role of observation and reinforcement in learning (Badghish et al., 2024). Effective use of technology for assessments likely contributes to better student engagement and satisfaction.

Table 7. *Level of Technological Integration: Digital Learning Platforms*

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
Our teachers regularly use digital platforms such as Quipper.	4.17	0.914	High
Our teachers' regular use of digital learning platforms positively impacts my learning motivation.	3.93	0.951	High
Our teachers' regular use of available multimedia elements in our digital learning platform positively contributes to my engagement in class.	3.96	0.827	High
Our teachers' regular use of our digital learning platforms allows us to access digital materials that are helpful in the learning process.	4.05	0.919	High
Our teachers' digital learning platforms are mobile-friendly and accessible on various devices (e.g., laptops, tablets, smartphones).	4.13	0.878	High
Overall indicator mean	4.05	0.902	High

Table 7 shows that the highest mean value of 4.17, with an SD of 0.914, is for the statement, "Our teachers regularly use digital platforms such as Quipper," indicating a high level of technological integration. This aligns with Schunk and Usher (2019), who suggest that positive outcomes motivate teachers to use technology, enhancing accuracy, efficiency, and engagement in the classroom. Conversely, the lowest mean value of 3.93, with an SD of 0.951, is for the statement, "Our teachers' regular use of digital learning platforms positively impacts my learning motivation," which still reflects a high level of integration but suggests that the impact on motivation may not be as strong.

The overall mean value for technological integration in digital learning platforms is 4.05, with an SD of 0.902, indicating a high level of integration. This is supported by Eze, Chinedu-Eze, and Bello (2018), who found that digital platforms enhance learning experiences and interaction between students and instructors. The results are consistent with Social Cognitive Theory, which highlights the role of observation and modeling in learning (Badghish et al., 2024), emphasizing that teachers' regular use of digital platforms can improve students' learning experiences and motivation.

Table 8. *Overall Level of Technological Integration*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description
Use of Technology in Teaching Learning	4.08	0.841	High
Technology Enhanced Assessment	4.05	0.809	High
Digital Learning Platforms	4.05	0.902	High
Overall variable mean	4.06	0.851	High

Table 8 provides an overview of technology integration in Junior High School English, focusing on three indicators: the use of technology in teaching-learning, technology-enhanced assessment, and digital learning platforms. The highest mean score is seen in the "Use of Technology in Teaching-Learning" indicator, with a mean of 4.08 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.841, indicating a high level of technological integration. This result is supported by Barker (2021), who highlights the increasing use of technology in education to equip students with 21st-century skills, improve academic performance, and enhance engagement. The high mean score suggests that effective technological integration significantly contributes to positive educational outcomes in English classrooms.

The lowest mean score is observed in the "Technology Enhanced Assessment" indicator, with a mean of 4.05 and an SD of 0.809, which still reflects a high level of integration. Liaw (2019) notes that technology-enhanced assessments offer personalized learning experiences that cater to different learning paces and styles, fostering a more engaging and effective learning environment. Despite challenges, these assessments benefit student learning and engagement, aligning with the high mean score.

Overall, the level of technological integration in Junior High School English is high, with an overall mean of 4.06 and an SD of 0.851, consistent with studies by Bhat (2023) and Schunk and Usher (2019), who emphasize the positive impact of technology on student outcomes and engagement.

Level of Student Engagement

The following table shows the result of every question provided per indicator about the level of Student Engagement of Junior High School English Students.

Table 9 shows the level of student engagement among junior high school English students, with the highest value in the statement "I regularly attend class and arrive punctually," having a mean score of 4.38 and an SD of 0.835. Pishghadam et al. (2019) support this high engagement level and note that regular attendance, often driven by educator encouragement, dramatically increases the likelihood of high academic achievement. The lowest value is found in the statement, "I consistently complete assignments and tasks on time," with a mean score of 3.59 and an SD of 0.982. Rahman et al. (2024) identify various factors contributing to students delaying task completion, including anxiety, low self-esteem, and disorganization.

Table 9. Student Engagement: Behavioral Engagement

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
I demonstrate enthusiasm and interest in the subject matter.	3.86	0.785	High
I regularly attend class and arrive punctually.	4.38	0.835	Very high
I take the initiative to ask questions or seek clarification when needed.	3.72	0.980	High
I actively listen to my peers and the instructor during lectures or presentations.	4.11	0.800	High
I consistently complete assignments and tasks on time.	3.59	0.982	High
Overall indicator mean	3.93	0.903	High

The overall mean score for student engagement is 3.93, with an SD of 0.923, indicating a high level of engagement among junior high school English students. Foster (2023) highlights that this engagement includes active involvement in learning activities, classroom participation, and school events. Social Cognitive Theory, as discussed by Schunk and Usher (2019), suggests that positive social environments and self-regulatory behaviors influence high engagement levels. Teachers and peers reinforce regular attendance and punctuality, while the supportive learning environment helps maintain consistent assignment completion.

Table 10. Student Engagement: Emotional Engagement

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
I am motivated to participate actively in class activities.	3.78	0.948	High
I feel a sense of connection and belonging in my classroom.	3.74	0.970	High
I feel supported by my classmates and instructor in this class.	3.79	0.980	High
I feel emotionally engaged and invested in my learning experience.	3.79	0.882	High
I feel valued and respected by my instructor.	4.03	0.854	High
Overall indicator mean	3.83	0.926	High

Table 10 shows the level of emotional engagement among junior high school English students. The highest value is in the statement, "I feel valued and respected by my instructor," with a mean score of 4.03 and an SD of 0.854, indicating high student engagement. Hagenauer et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of positive teacher-student relationships for enhancing learning and outcomes. The lowest value is in the statement, "I feel a sense of connection and belonging in my classroom," with a mean score of 3.74 and an SD of 0.970, which still indicates high engagement. Palomo and Chagas (2022) highlight that school belongingness is crucial for academic motivation and success.

The overall mean score for emotional engagement is 3.83, with an SD of 0.926, indicating high emotional engagement among junior high school English students. This aligns with Hollister et al. (2022), who suggest that the learning environment and interpersonal relationships influence emotional engagement. As discussed by Epstein and Dattilio (2020), Social Cognitive Learning Theory underscores the importance of the social environment in shaping students' emotional engagement. The supportive and respectful interactions between students and instructors and a sense of connection and belonging are crucial for fostering high emotional engagement.

Table 11. Student Engagement: Cognitive Engagement

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
I am challenged to think critically in this class.	4.14	0.746	High
I can apply problem-solving skills to tasks and assignments.	3.91	0.842	High
I am motivated to delve deeper into the subject matter outside class.	3.81	0.846	High
I actively seek to understand complex concepts presented in class.	3.96	0.813	High
I am encouraged to explore different perspectives on course topics.	4.07	0.791	High
Overall indicator mean	3.98	0.815	High

Table 11 shows the level of cognitive engagement among junior high school English students. The highest value is in the statement, "I am challenged to think critically in this class," with a mean score of 4.14 and an SD of 0.746, indicating high engagement. Saleh (2019) supports this, stating that critical thinking involves deep reflection and thoughtful inquiry, enabling students to engage deeply with course material and actively participate in discussions. The lowest value is in the statement, "I am motivated to delve deeper into the subject matter outside of class," with a mean score of 3.81 and an SD of 0.846, still reflecting high engagement. Holm (2020) notes that technology and the internet allow students to explore English learning beyond the classroom, fostering more profound engagement.

The overall mean score for cognitive engagement is 3.98, with an SD of 0.815, indicating high engagement among junior high school English students. This aligns with Foster's (2023) definition of cognitive engagement as the mental effort and focus students apply to learning tasks, demonstrating curiosity and a thirst for knowledge. As discussed by Dodgers et al. (2023), Social Cognitive Learning Theory highlights the role of social interactions in fostering cognitive engagement. The high engagement levels observed can be attributed to an interactive and supportive learning environment that encourages students to engage deeply with the material, enhancing their cognitive skills and academic performance.

Table 12 provides an overview of student engagement among Junior High School English students. The highest value is in Cognitive Engagement, with a mean score of 3.98 and an SD of 0.815, indicating high engagement. Hollister et al. (2022) describe cognitive engagement as involving deep learning, self-regulation, and sustained mental effort, fostering profound understanding and intellectual

growth. The lowest value is in Emotional Engagement, with a mean score of 3.83 and an SD of 0.926, indicating high engagement. Foster (2023) defines emotional engagement as the enthusiasm and reactions students have toward their learning experiences, highlighting the importance of emotional investment and curiosity in learning.

Table 12. *Overall Level of Student Engagement*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Behavioral Engagement	3.93	0.923	High
Emotional Engagement	3.83	0.926	High
Cognitive Engagement	3.98	0.815	High
Overall variable mean	3.91	0.892	High

Overall, the result of 3.91 with an SD of 0.892 demonstrates consistently high student engagement in Junior High School English. This aligns with Bond et al. (2020), who emphasize that high engagement enhances educational enthusiasm and long-term success. Nickerson (2024) supports the importance of social cognitive theory, highlighting the role of social context and interactions in learning. The high cognitive and emotional engagement levels can be attributed to a positive classroom environment where students feel motivated, challenged, and connected to their learning community.

Correlations Analysis between the Variables of Interest of the Study

Table 13. *Correlations Analysis between Variables Interactive Teaching Method and Student Engagement*

	<i>Interactive Teaching Method</i>	<i>Student Engagement</i>
Interactive Teaching Method	1	0.648
Student Engagement	0.648	1

Table 13 presents the correlation between interactive teaching methods and student engagement, showing a correlation coefficient of 0.648. This indicates a moderately positive relationship between the two variables. The findings align with a study by Kamran et al. (2022), which emphasized that interactive teaching methods effectively facilitate diverse learning styles and create a more inclusive educational environment. These methods promote active student engagement, capture attention, and enhance information retention. Furthermore, another study by Kamran et al. (2023) defines interactive teaching methods as instructional strategies that encourage student involvement in learning, fostering collaboration and critical thinking. This active participation of students contributes to a robust educational environment.

Additionally, these findings align with the Social Cognitive Theory, as discussed in the study by Bajcar and Babel (2018), which highlights the impact of the school's social environment on children's social and moral development. This theory supports the positive relationship between interactive teaching methods and student engagement, reinforcing that these methods contribute to a more solid educational setting by promoting collaboration and critical thinking. The Social Cognitive Theory underscores the influence of the school's social environment on students' development, further supporting the effectiveness of interactive teaching methods in creating a robust educational environment.

Table 14. *Correlations Table between Technology Integration and Student Engagement*

	<i>Technology Integration</i>	<i>Student Engagement</i>
Technology Integration	1	0.537
Student Engagement	0.537	1

In Table 14, the correlation between technology integration and student engagement is 0.537, indicating a moderate positive relationship between the two variables. This finding is consistent with the literature by Abrigo et al. (2019), which suggests that integrating technology improves student engagement and performance. Educators can create comprehensive and engaging learning experiences that capture students' interest and encourage active engagement by incorporating technological tools and resources. Additionally, Katyara et al. (2023) found that using technology tools influences student behavioral engagement, demonstrating a positive and significant relationship between technology and students' behavioral engagement, thus making learners more actively involved in learning activities. This literature supports the moderately positive relationship between technology integration and student engagement.

Furthermore, to support this result within the theoretical framework, as Nickerson (2024) highlighted, social cognitive theory emphasizes the role of the social context in learning. The theory suggests that individuals are active participants who can both exert influence on and be influenced by their environment. In the context of technology integration and student engagement, social cognitive theory suggests that technology provides opportunities for social interactions, observational learning, and the development of self-efficacy, all of which contribute to increased student engagement, as observed in the correlation between technology integration and student engagement.

Regression Analysis Between Variables of Interest of the Study

Utilizing linear regression analysis, the researchers seek to determine the strength of the relations between the variables of the study.

The results of the analysis are as follows:

Table 15. Test of Influence of Interactive Teaching Method on Student Engagement

Variable	Standardized Coefficient Beta	B	Standard Error	T value
Interactive Teaching Methods	0.603	0.648	0.048	12.654
Constant	1.484		0.194	7.648
Multiple R	0.648	Moderate Positive Correlations		
R2	0.420			
Adjusted R2	0.417			

Table 15 regression analysis reveals a significant impact of interactive teaching methods on student engagement, with a beta value of 0.648, a t-value of 12.654, and a p-value of 0.000. This indicates a strong positive relationship, showing that approximately 42% of the variation in student engagement can be attributed to interactive teaching methods (adjusted R-squared = 0.417).

These findings align with Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, which posits that learning occurs through active participation and observation (Nickerson, 2024). Interactive teaching methods foster collaboration and hands-on experiences, enhancing understanding, critical thinking, and independent exploration. This approach benefits academic performance and social-emotional development, preparing students for dynamic learning environments.

Supporting studies by Kamran et al. (2023) and Kishore (2023) confirm that interactive teaching methods boost engagement, retention, and academic performance. Based on these results, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis—stating that interactive teaching methods significantly influence student engagement—is accepted.

Table 16. Test of Influence of Technological Integration on Student Engagement

Variable	Standardized Coefficient Beta	B	Standard Error	T value	P value	Alpha Value	Interpretation
Technology Integration	0.549	0.537	0.058	9.454	0.000	0.05	Significant
Constant	1.685		0.238	7.086	0.000		
Multiple R	0.537	Moderate Positive Correlations					
R2	0.288						
Adjusted R2	0.285						

Table 16 shows a significant impact of perceived technological integration on student engagement, with a beta value of 0.537, a t-value of 9.454, and a p-value of 0.000. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.285 indicates that 28.5% of the variation in student engagement is due to perceived technological integration.

This aligns with social cognitive theory, which suggests that individuals are motivated by anticipated positive outcomes (Schunk & Usher, 2019). Technology in the classroom can motivate students, increasing their engagement through multimedia resources and interactive tools.

Supporting studies by Pittas and Adeyemi (2019) and Mohebi (2022) confirm that technology enhances teaching and learning, fostering higher cognitive engagement and effectiveness.

The regression results and literature support the conclusion that interactive teaching methods and technology integration significantly influence student engagement. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis. Educators should recognize the value of these strategies as they enhance teaching practices, promote student participation, and create dynamic, personalized learning environments that meet educational standards and improve learning outcomes.

Conclusions

This study examined the impact of interactive teaching methods and technology integration on student engagement among Junior High School English students. Findings revealed that both interactive teaching methods, with a mean score of 4.03, and technology integration, with a mean score of 4.06, significantly enhance student engagement. Correlation analysis showed moderately positive relationships between interactive teaching methods, student engagement ($r = 0.648$), and technology integration and student engagement ($r = 0.537$). Regression analysis indicated that interactive teaching methods ($p = 0.000$, $\beta = 0.603$) account for 42% of the variance in student engagement, while technology integration ($p = 0.000$, $\beta = 0.549$) explains 28.8%. These results align with previous studies by Kamran et al. (2022), Afzal et al. (2022), Abrigo et al. (2019), and Katyara et al. (2023), confirming the critical role of interactive teaching methods and technology in fostering student engagement.

The study reveals that interactive teaching methods and technological integration significantly influenced student engagement, with a moderately positive correlation between these factors and engagement in Junior High School English classes. Although the overall level of interactive teaching methods is high, fostering student empowerment needs improvement. Schools may incorporate more student-centered activities, invest in teacher training for these strategies, and enhance technology-enhanced assessments through

targeted professional development. Though emotional engagement requires further attention; thus, teachers may create a supportive classroom environment. Additionally, continuous professional development in both interactive methods and technology will ensure these tools effectively boost engagement, as emphasized by Social Cognitive Theory (Bajcar & Babel, 2018; Nickerson, 2024).

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